

Farmer categorization based on farmer performance index: identifying the targets of agricultural extension

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Careful identification of target groups is essential in any effective agricultural extension program. Since one of the objectives of agricultural extension is to increase crop yield, efforts should be exerted to clearly identify the target audience. Blanket recommendations have given marginal returns to investments. In this context, the farmer performance index (FPI) can be used to categorize farmers who can be targeted as recipients of extension programs. Pingali et al (1990) have defined FPI as the ratio of farmers' actual yield to location-specific yield (LSY) potential. The main advantage of using FPI in agricultural extension programs is the assurance that extension targets can be identified for different technological packages.

An investigation was carried out in Shrawasthipura and Rambewa villages of Anuradhapura District (dry zone), Sri Lanka. The two villages are dominated by tank-fed rice culture. A field survey was done just after the major rice-growing season in 2001-02 (*maha*, Oct-Feb) and 25 farmers from each village were selected randomly. Pretested questionnaires were used to gather data on yield performance.

LSY was calculated by taking the average rice yield in the last 5 years. This was found to be 4.3 t ha⁻¹. The FPI values were calculated for the farmers selected in the two villages (see figure). The

results indicate that, in Shrawasthipura and Rambewa, 44% and 36% of farmers had yields below LSY, respectively. Farmers were then categorized according to actual yields that they obtained. The table illustrates the farmer categorization.

Farmer categorization on the basis of FPI.

Yield category	Percentage of farmers	
	Shrawasthipura	Rambewa
Low (below 4 t ha ⁻¹)	28	16
Medium (4–5 t ha ⁻¹)	52	64
High (above 5 t ha ⁻¹)	20	20

This type of farmer categorization characterizes the targets of agricultural extension programs with further identification of farmers' needs. For example, the

low yielders are represented by 28% and 16% of farmers in Shrawasthipura and Rambewa, respectively. To reduce the gap between LSY and actual yield, major limitations encountered in this category should be identified and extension interventions be directed to remove such limitations.

Reference

Pingali PC, Moya PF, Velasco LE. 1990. The post-green revolution blues in Asian rice production. Manila (Philippines): International Rice Research Institute.

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Farmer performance index

Farmer performance index of farmer-respondents in Shrawasthipura and Rambewa, Anuradhapura, Sri Lanka, 2001-02.